

DETECTING TEMPORAL RELATIONS IN ARCHAEOLOGY: MODEL AND ALGORITHMS

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ABSTRACT. This paper addresses the question of finding the optimal temporal relation between two time-periods, in the presence of uncertainties regarding their boundaries (i.e., unknown or bounded start/end). It proposes a fast algorithmic solution, implemented in the Python language, and an archaeological case study related to the Early Bronze Age in the Levant. Open-source Python implementations of our data model and algorithms can be downloaded on the author’s GitHub repository. Our solution is also implemented in the latest version (v. 3) of the ChronoLog modelling tool (<https://chrono.ulb.be/>).

1. INTRODUCTION

Temporal relations are mathematical objects expressing how two time-periods (a.k.a. time-intervals) relate to each other chronologically. Since archaeology is strongly involved with the study of time and its representation, temporal relations are naturally relevant in this field. The best-known formal system of temporal relations is that of James Allen (Allen 1983; Allen 1984) which, though not originally designed for archaeology, is often quoted in archaeological literature (see Levy 2025, p. 180-181, for a list of references). In a recent paper (Levy 2025), we argued that archaeology necessitates an alternative, more complex, system of temporal relations, and presented the details of such a system, inspired by the relations present in the ChronoLog modelling tool¹. This system is presented in Tables 1 and 2 below². Its relevance for archaeology is illustrated in Table 3, through a list of quotes from archaeological literature, modelled using temporal relations.

This paper builds on the above-mentioned system of temporal relations, and investigates how to detect the strongest (i.e., the most precise) temporal relation connecting two given time-periods. Clearly, several different relations can hold at the same time. For example, the lives of Winston Churchill (1874-1965) and Elizabeth II (1926-2022) are related in several ways: (1) Churchill and Elizabeth were *contemporaries* (they were both alive between 1926 and 1965), (2) Churchill’s lifetime *includes the start* of Elizabeth’s, (3) Churchill’s lifetime *ended during* Elizabeth’s, and (4) Churchill’s lifetime *overlaps* Elizabeth’s, with Churchill’s starting first. These relations correspond, respectively, to relations 5 (Contemporary), 6b (Includes start of), 7a (Ends during) and 8a (Overlaps before) in our typology (cf. Table 1). The strongest of these relations is “Churchill *overlaps before* Elizabeth” (rel. 8a), as this relation directly implies the other three (see Fig 1).

The above question was relatively easy to answer, as we know the exact birth and death dates of these persons. In archaeology, however, time-periods often feature uncertain or unknown boundaries, deriving, for example, from radiocarbon results

¹For more details on ChronoLog, see Levy et al. 2021; Levy, Geeraerts, and Pluquet In press. ChronoLog is available for download at <https://chrono.ulb.be/>.

²This article only deals with the core system outlined in Levy 2025 (relations 1–15). It does not address the extra relations 16-26, which are mere variants of the core relations, based on the use of strict rather than inclusive inequalities.

or partial historical knowledge. Detecting the strongest relation in such a setting can be challenging. Say Alice was born between 1910 and 1930, and died between 1940 and 1980. Bob was born between 1900 and 1920, and died between 1950 and 1970. What is the strongest temporal relation connecting Alice and Bob? Here, the answer is: Alice and Bob are *contemporary* with each other (note they were both alive between 1930 and 1940), and it can be shown that no strongest relation (such as *overlap*, *inclusion*, or *starts/ends during*) holds. Another interesting case is the following: what if Alice was born between 1901 and 1930 and died between 1920 and 1945, and Bob was born between 1915 and 1925, and died between 1921 and 1950? Here, it can be shown that no relation holds between Alice and Bob (among all those of our typology). Detecting such cases of absence of relation can also be challenging. We believe that providing an automated method to help archaeologists easily derive the strongest temporal relation between two such time-periods is a *desideratum*, and we are not aware of any current software solution offering this functionality. This is all the more needed, as archaeologists are often confronted with numerous time-periods, which would make the manual derivation of the strongest relation for each pair of periods extremely tedious.

The goal of this paper is to provide a practical algorithmic solution to this problem, which can be used by computational archaeologists to analyze their datasets within their own computational pipelines. Our solution is implemented in Python, but is simple enough as to be easily translatable into other programming languages. The structure of the paper is as follows. In order to find the strongest relation among two periods, the full structure of logical implications between our temporal relations needs to be explored, a subject which we only partially explored previously (Levy 2025, p. 189-192). This structure is explored in Sec. 2. We then present our data model, which allows for uncertainties in the boundaries of time-periods (Sec. 3). Sec. 4 presents our algorithms for finding the strongest relation among two time-periods. Finally, Sec. 5 provides a short case study illustrating our approach.

The full Python code of our data structures, algorithms, benchmarks and case study is freely available for download on this paper’s GitHub repository³ and is also archived on Zenodo⁴.

2. LOGICAL IMPLICATIONS BETWEEN TEMPORAL RELATIONS

Fig. 1 presents the full system of implications between our relations⁵. We say that a relation R *implies* a relation S if when R holds for any two time-periods, S holds as well. For example, relation *Equals* implies relation *Starts with*, since when two periods are chronologically equal, they necessarily start at the same time. The structure of the implications consists of a directed acyclic graph (DAG), where an arrow between two relations R and S expresses that R implies S. The DAG has been transitively reduced⁶.

The given layout of the DAG emphasizes the hierarchical structure of the temporal relations, with stronger relations (in terms of implication) drawn higher up in the graph, and weaker ones drawn lower. *Equals*, *Meets*, and *Met by* are the strongest relations in the structure, as they are not implied by any other. In the same way, *Starts before or at end of* and *Ends after or at start of* are the weakest ones, as they do not imply any other relation.

³See <https://github.com/Eythan31/Temporal-relations>.

⁴See <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20766168>.

⁵This graph generalizes and completes the partial implication graphs shown in Levy 2025 (Figs. 2-5).

⁶The transitive reduction of a DAG excludes edges which can be deduced by transitivity (say, if R implies S, and S implies T, then the DAG will not connect R to T).

ID	Generic name	Relation and inverse	Definition
1	START-END ORDER	1a. <i>A starts before or at end of B</i>	$\text{beg}(A) \leq \text{end}(B)$
		1b. <i>A ends after or at start of B</i>	$\text{end}(A) \geq \text{beg}(B)$
2	START ORDER	2a. <i>A starts before or at start of B</i>	$\text{beg}(A) \leq \text{beg}(B)$
		2b. <i>A starts after or at start of B</i>	$\text{beg}(A) \geq \text{beg}(B)$
3	END ORDER	3a. <i>A ends before or at end of B</i>	$\text{end}(A) \leq \text{end}(B)$
		3b. <i>A ends after or at end of B</i>	$\text{end}(A) \geq \text{end}(B)$
4	DISJUNCTION	4a. <i>A ends before or at start of B</i>	$\text{end}(A) \leq \text{beg}(B)$
		4b. <i>A starts after or at end of B</i>	$\text{beg}(A) \geq \text{end}(B)$
5	CONTEMPORANEITY	5. <i>A contemporary with B</i>	$\text{end}(A) \geq \text{beg}(B)$ AND $\text{beg}(A) \leq \text{end}(B)$
6	START INCLUSION	6a. <i>A starts during B</i>	$\text{beg}(B) \leq \text{beg}(A) \leq \text{end}(B)$
		6b. <i>A includes start of B</i>	$\text{beg}(A) \leq \text{beg}(B) \leq \text{end}(A)$
7	END INCLUSION	7a. <i>A ends during B</i>	$\text{beg}(B) \leq \text{end}(A) \leq \text{end}(B)$
		7b. <i>A includes ends of B</i>	$\text{beg}(A) \leq \text{end}(B) \leq \text{end}(A)$
8	OVERLAP	8a. <i>A overlaps before B</i>	$\text{beg}(A) \leq \text{beg}(B) \leq \text{end}(A) \leq \text{end}(B)$
		8b. <i>A overlaps after B</i>	$\text{beg}(B) \leq \text{beg}(A) \leq \text{end}(B) \leq \text{end}(A)$
9	INCLUSION	9a. <i>A includes B</i>	$\text{beg}(A) \leq \text{beg}(B)$ AND $\text{end}(A) \geq \text{end}(B)$
		9b. <i>A included in B</i>	$\text{beg}(A) \geq \text{beg}(B)$ AND $\text{end}(A) \leq \text{end}(B)$
10	EQUAL START	10. <i>A starts with B</i>	$\text{beg}(A) = \text{beg}(B)$
11	EQUAL END	11. <i>A ends with B</i>	$\text{end}(A) = \text{end}(B)$
12	SEQUENCE	12a. <i>A meets B</i>	$\text{end}(A) = \text{beg}(B)$
		12b. <i>A met by B</i>	$\text{beg}(A) = \text{end}(B)$
13	BEGINNING	13a. <i>A begins B</i>	$\text{beg}(A) = \text{beg}(B)$ AND $\text{end}(A) \leq \text{end}(B)$
		13b. <i>A begun by B</i>	$\text{beg}(A) = \text{beg}(B)$ AND $\text{end}(A) \geq \text{end}(B)$
14	ENDING	14a. <i>A ends B</i>	$\text{end}(A) = \text{end}(B)$ AND $\text{beg}(A) \geq \text{beg}(B)$
		14b. <i>A ended by B</i>	$\text{beg}(A) \leq \text{beg}(B)$ AND $\text{end}(A) = \text{end}(B)$
15	EQUALITY	15. <i>A equals B</i>	$\text{beg}(A) = \text{beg}(B)$ AND $\text{end}(A) = \text{end}(B)$

TABLE 1. Levy's system of temporal relations (after Levy 2025, with adapted ID numbers).

ID	Generic name	Relation	Image	Inverse relation	Image
1	START-END ORDER	1a. <i>A starts before or at end of B</i>		1b. <i>A ends after or at start of B</i>	
2	START ORDER	2a. <i>A starts before or at start of B</i>		2b. <i>A starts after or at start of B</i>	
3	END ORDER	3a. <i>A ends before or at end of B</i>		3b. <i>A ends after or at end of B</i>	
4	DISJUNCTION	4a. <i>A ends before or at start of B</i>		4b. <i>A starts after or at end of B</i>	
5	CONTEMPORANEITY	5. <i>A contemporary with B</i>			
6	START INCLUSION	6a. <i>A starts during B</i>		6b. <i>A includes start of B</i>	
7	END INCLUSION	7a. <i>A ends during B</i>		7b. <i>A includes ends of B</i>	
8	OVERLAP	8a. <i>A overlaps before B</i>		8b. <i>A overlaps after B</i>	
9	INCLUSION	9a. <i>A includes B</i>		9b. <i>A included in B</i>	
10	EQUAL START	10. <i>A starts with B</i>			
11	EQUAL END	11. <i>A ends with B</i>			
12	SEQUENCE	12a. <i>A meets B</i>		12b. <i>A met by B</i>	
13	BEGINNING	13a. <i>A begins B</i>		13b. <i>A begun by B</i>	
14	ENDING	14a. <i>A ends B</i>		14b. <i>A ended by B</i>	
15	EQUALITY	15. <i>A equals B</i>			

TABLE 2. Graphical illustrations of our system of temporal relations. Circles represent period boundaries and dotted lines represent uncertainty as to the position of a boundary.

ID	Relation	Quote	Modelling
1	START-END ORDER	“there can be no doubt that LC IA started before the end of the Second Intermediate Period” (Merrillees 1992, p. 50)	LC IA starts before or at the end of the Second Intermediate Period
2	START ORDER	“the introduction of LH III A2 pottery appears to precede LM III A2” (Wiener 2003, p. 241)	LH III A2 starts before or at the start of LM III A2
3	END ORDER	“Megiddo VA-IVB was destroyed earlier than Jezreel” (Ben-Tor and Ben-Ami 1998, p. 34)	Megiddo VA-IVB ends before or at the end of Jezreel
4	DISJUNCTION	“[Lachish] Level II was constructed after an occupation gap and appears to be less monumental in nature than Level III” (Garfinkel et al. 2021, p. 423)	Lachish Level III ends before or at the start of Level II
5	CONTEMPORANEITY	“an LH III A1 vase in the LM III A1 Sellopoulo Tomb 4 [...] shows that these [...] periods were at least partly contemporary” (Warren and Hankey 1989, p. 84)	LH III A1 is contemporary with LM III A1
6	START INCLUSION	“LH III A 2 had already begun within the time of LM III A1” (Warren and Hankey 1989, p. 84)	LH III A 2 starts during LM III A1
7	END INCLUSION	“In Crete, the palace at Knossos is destroyed in LM/LH IIIA2” (Wiener 2003, p. 240)	Knossos Palace ends during LM/LH IIIA2
8	OVERLAP	“an overlap of early Dyn. 14 and the end of Dyn. 12” (Schneider 2006, p. 169)	Dyn. 12 overlaps before Dyn. 14
9	INCLUSION	“all three burials in Tomb 4 occurred within the short span of the [LM] IIIA1 stage” (Popham, Catling, and Catling 1974, p. 206).	Tomb 4 is included in LM IIIA1
10	EQUAL START	“Argive LG II should therefore begin at the same time as Attic LG IIa” (Coldstream 2008, p. 145)	Argive LG II starts with Attic LG IIa
11	EQUAL END	“It can be inferred that the [Megiddo Stratum VII] gate was destroyed at the same time as the adjacent palace.” (Ussishkin 2021, p. 481)	The Megiddo Stratum VII gate ends with the Megiddo Stratum VII palace
12	SEQUENCE	“Khephren succeeded his brother Ra’djedef in Dyn. 4” (Bierbrier 2006, p. 40)	Ra’djedef meets Khephren
13	BEGINNING	“the archaeological period called Iron IIA, the first phase of the Iron Age II” (Schloen 2015, p. 434)	Iron IIA begins Iron II
14	ENDING	“The last phase of the Iron Age [...] is called Iron IIC in the southern Levant” (Schloen 2015, p. 435)	Iron IIC ends Iron II
15	EQUALITY	“the Aegean periods can be placed in workable chronological accord with the Cypriote periods: [...] MM IIB = Early LC III” (Warren and Hankey 1989, p. 118)	MM IIB equals Early LC III

TABLE 3. Examples of temporal relations, from archaeological literature (after Levy 2025, Table 7, with adapted ID numbers). Note that the example of relation 12 incorrectly appeared as “Khephren **meets** Ra’djedef” in Levy 2025, Table 7.

FIGURE 1. Full structure of implications between the temporal relations, expressed in the shape of a directed acyclic graph (DAG).

Note that the identification numbers (IDs) given to the temporal relations slightly differ from those in Levy 2025. They have been chosen to guarantee the following properties: (1) whenever a relation implies another relation, its ID is higher, (2) relations 1–4 are the four basic orderings between the boundaries (start and end) of two periods, (3) relations 5 and above are all special cases of contemporaneity⁷, (4) relations 10 and above involve at least one equality between boundaries.

3. DATA MODEL

3.1. Data model

Our data model comprises two types of objects: *periods*⁸ and *boundaries*. A *period* consists of two boundaries, representing its *start* and *end*. Boundaries can be:

- Known: say, “1914”
- Unknown: no temporal knowledge at all

⁷We are using the term “contemporaneity” in the sense of a non-empty intersection between two time-periods (see Levy, Piasetzky, and Fantalkin 2021, p. 184-185; Levy 2025, p. 188). In other words, two periods are contemporary in they have at least one unit of time in common.

⁸Regarding alignment with existing time ontologies, our concept of *period* corresponds to the CIDOC-CRM class “E2 Temporal Entity” (http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/E2_Temporal_Entity), and the OWL Time class “time:Interval” (<https://www.w3.org/TR/owl-time/#time:Interval>).

Python	Meaning
<code>Period()</code>	Unknown boundaries
<code>Period(start=1914)</code>	Known start
<code>Period(end=1918)</code>	Known end
<code>Period(start=After(1914))</code>	Lower-bounded start
<code>Period(end=Before(1918))</code>	Upper-bounded end
<code>Period(start=Range(1914,1918))</code>	Start in a range
<code>Period(start=After(1914), end=Before(1918))</code>	Bounded start and end
<code>Period(After(1914), Before(1918))</code>	Bounded start and end (alt. notation)
<code>Period(start=1914, end=1918)</code>	Known start and end
<code>Period(1914, 1918)</code>	Known start and end (alt. notation)

TABLE 4. Examples of encodings of time-periods in our data model. Keywords `Before` and `After` must be understood inclusively (i.e., “before or at” and “after or at”).

- Lower bounded: say, “1914 or later”
- Upper bounded: say, “1918 or earlier”
- In a range: say, “between 1914 and 1918”

The start and end boundaries of a period are modelled separately: for example, the start could be known (say, 1940), and the end be a range (say, [1950, 1960]). The model also assumes that boundaries can be compared to each other, for equality, anteriority, and posteriority. Note that such comparisons do not always have a clear answer: for example, if both periods A and B start within the range [1900, 2000], it is unknown whether they are equal, nor which one is earlier than the other. On the other hand, if A starts within [1900, 1930] and B starts within [1950, 1980], then A is known to start earlier than B.

3.2. Python implementation

We provide a Python implementation of our data model, consisting of a class `Boundary` and a class `Period` (full code in Appendices A.1 and A.2). The `Boundary` class contains a lower bound (earliest date, field `lb`) and an upper bound (latest date, field `ub`), both of which are optional (i.e., they can have `None` values). This allows for an easy implementation of the five configurations listed above (note that known boundaries use the same value for the lower and upper bound). Our implementation of boundaries features also derived classes `After`, `Before` and `Range`, for lower-bounded, upper-bounded and range boundaries, respectively.

The `Boundary` class also implements the three above-mentioned comparison operators (“`==`” for equality, “`<=`” for “earlier or equal”, and “`>=`” for “later or equal”). These operators return `True` if the relation holds, and `False` if it doesn’t hold or if the result is unknown due to chronological uncertainty. These operators can be used to easily implement the definitions of our temporal relations listed in Table 1, as shown by our Python dictionary `conditions` used in the algorithms below (full code in Appendix A.3). Table 4 presents some examples of declarations of time-periods within our data model, encoded using our Python class `Period`. Table 5 presents examples of strongest relations between pairs of time-periods.

Period A		Period B		Strongest Relation
Start	End	Start	End	
[1,5]	[1,5]	2	4	0. No relation
[1,3]	[1,5]			1a. Starts before or at end of
1	[1,5]			2a. Starts before or at start of
[1,4]	[1,4]			3a. Ends before or at end of
1	[1,2]			4a. Ends before or at start of
[1,3]	[3,5]			5. Contemporary with
3	[3,5]			6a. Starts during
[1,3]	3			7a. Ends during
1	3			8a. Overlaps before
1	5			9a. Includes
2	[3,5]			10. Starts with
[1,3]	4			11. Ends with
1	2			12a. Meets
2	3			13a. Begins
3	4			14a. Ends
2	4			15. Equals

TABLE 5. Simple examples of strongest relations between two periods. Inverse relations are omitted for the sake of conciseness.

4. ALGORITHMS

This section presents two different approaches to detect the strongest relation between two periods. The first approach is top-down, based on topological sorting (Algorithm 1). The second is bottom up, and based on depth-first search (Algorithm 2). The second approach will be further simplified (Algorithms 3 and 4), in order to reduce its execution time.

4.1. Algorithm 1: top-down approach

Algorithm 1 (Fig. 2) is the simplest in our series. It follows a top-down approach: test each relation according to a topological order of the DAG, and stop whenever a relation is found to hold true. This relation is guaranteed to be the strongest one, by definition of a topological order⁹. A simple look at our DAG (Fig. 1) shows that the decreasing order of relation IDs (i.e., 15 to 1, regardless of the order of a/b relations) is a topological order, which simply chooses the relations from the top to the bottom layer of the DAG. An extra relation 0 was added to the dictionary of conditions, symbolizing the absence of relation between the two periods. This relation is returned automatically at the end of the loop if no other relation holds. Note that this algorithm will be fast on strong relations (e.g., 15, 14, 13) but slower

⁹Recall that a topological order in a DAG is an order in which a node is treated only after all its predecessors have been treated. It is thus a total order coherent with the DAG's partial order.

```

all_relations = ["0", "1a", "1b", "2a", "2b", "3a", "3b", \
                "4a", "4b", "5", "6a", "6b", "7a", "7b", \
                "8a", "8b", "9a", "9b", "10", "11", "12a", \
                "12b", "13a", "13b", "14a", "14b", "15"]

def alg1(a, b): # a and b are Period objects
    for relation in reversed(all_relations):
        if condition[relation](a, b):
            return relation

```

FIGURE 2. Algorithm 1: topological order. The `condition` structure is detailed in Appendix A.3.

on weak ones (e.g., 1, 2, 3) as the latter are examined last. Furthermore, the algorithm also wastes some time by retesting the same conditions several times: for example, the condition $\text{beg}(A)=\text{beg}(B)$ is tested in relation 15, then potentially again in relations 13a and 13b. On the other hand, the algorithm has the advantage of being simple, short, easy to implement, and requires no additional data structures besides the conditions defining the temporal relations.

4.2. Algorithm 2: bottom-up approach

As noted above, Algorithm 1, though fast and elegant, is expected to run slowly on low-level temporal relations, as these are explored last by the algorithm. However, such weak relations are often the most common ones, hence the need for an algorithm better suited for them. Such an algorithm would need to run *bottom-up*, evaluating low-level relations before high-level ones. This section describes the engineering of such an algorithm in three steps, successively refining it in order to make it faster and more memory-efficient.

4.2.1. *Algorithm 2a: depth-first search.* Our first approach is based on depth-first search (Fig. 3a). It works on an inverted version of the DAG, where the edges run upward and represent the “implied by” relationship (Fig. 3b). This DAG also features an additional root node 0, connected to nodes 1a and 1b, and used to start the algorithm. The algorithm’s idea is simple: the strongest relation is one which holds true, but whose neighbors (i.e., stronger relations) do not. This can be directly implemented by DFS: if a relation R does not hold (or if it was already tested before), the algorithm returns `None`. If the relation does hold, its neighbors are inspected in turn. If one of these neighbors holds true, the algorithm is applied to that neighbor. If none of the neighbors hold true, then R is the strongest relation. In case no relation holds, 0 is returned at the end. This algorithm requires an explicit implementation of the inverted DAG, provided here as a dictionary associating the relation’s ID to the list of its neighbors (Appendix A.4). The algorithm also requires boolean marks, as in standard DFS, in order to avoid exploring the same node twice. This algorithm is more complex than Algorithm 1 and requires an additional data structure (the DAG). It also has additional overhead due to the recursive calls and the handling of node marks. Yet, since it starts with the weak relations, it is expected to run faster for these. A comparison of running times of the two algorithms is presented in Fig. 7. It shows that Algorithm 2a is faster than Algorithm 1 for relations 0 to 4, but slower for relations 5 to 15.

4.2.2. *Algorithm 2b: tree traversal.* Algorithm 2b (Fig. 4) improves Algorithm 2a by explicitly encoding a depth-first search tree, and exploring that tree instead of the full inverted DAG. The tree structure is presented in Fig. 4, and its Python implementation in Appendix A.6. That tree, if explored in depth-first order following

```

def DFS(node, a, b, marked): # helper function (Depth-First Search)
    if not marked[node]:
        marked[node] = True
        if not condition[node](a,b):
            return None
        for neighbor in graph[node]:
            rel = DFS(neighbor, a, b, marked)
            if rel is not None:
                return rel
        return node
    return None

def alg2a(a, b): # main function (a and b are Period objects)
    return DFS("0", a, b, {rel:False for rel in all_relations})

```

(a) Python implementation. The `condition` and `graph` structures are detailed in Appendices A.3 and A.4.

(b) Data structure (inverted DAG)

FIGURE 3. Algorithm 2a: depth-first search in the inverted DAG.

the precise order of the adjacency lists given in our implementation, exactly mimics one particular execution of the DFS on the previous DAG (one that explores neighbors from left to right in Fig. 3b), and clears us from the need to encode all the edges from the DAG: only the edges that are actually explored (i.e., those that

do not lead to a node previously encountered) are explicitly represented¹⁰. This approach has the following advantages:

- (1) Simpler data structure: every node has at most one predecessor (by definition of a tree), resulting in no need for marking the nodes.
- (2) Faster checking of conditions: since only one path can lead to each node (by definition of a tree), one can simplify the condition tested for each relation, as parts of the condition have already been tested in the previous nodes of the path. For example, when testing relation 5, we know that relation 1a has already been tested, hence the condition $end(A) \geq beg(B) \text{ AND } beg(A) \leq end(B)$ simplifies to just $end(A) \geq beg(B)$. These reduced conditions are presented in Appendix A.5.

Our benchmarks (Fig. 7) show that Algorithm 2b is indeed faster than Algorithm 2a, and is faster than Algorithm 1 for relations 0 to 10.

4.2.3. *Algorithm 2c: explicit decision tree.* Algorithm 2c (Fig. 5) can be seen as an improved, data structure-free, implementation of Algorithm 2b. Here, the search tree is replaced by an *explicit* decision tree, where a series of nested *if* conditionals directly implements the shortened conditions used in Algorithm 2b. The advantage of this algorithm is its simplicity: no data structures are used, thus reducing overhead as much as possible. The algorithm uses only *if* conditionals, making it easily implementable in any programming language. The downside is the algorithm’s rather lengthy and cumbersome aspect. Our benchmarks (Fig. 7) show that Algorithm 2c is faster than Algorithm 2b. It also beats Algorithm 1 in almost every case: it is faster for relations 0 to 14a, and only slightly slower for relations 14b and 15.

4.3. Comparisons

Fig. 6 compares the execution times of the four algorithms on one million relations chosen uniformly at random. It shows that Algorithm 2c is the fastest, followed by Algorithm 2b, then by Algorithm 1. Algorithm 2a is the slowest. Fig. 7 then compares the four algorithms’ execution times, relation by relation, using one hundred thousand repetitions of each type of relation. It shows that Algorithm 1’s execution time globally decreases when one moves from weaker to strongest relations, due to its top-down approach. On the other hand, the execution time of Algorithms 2a–2c globally increases when moving from weaker to stronger relations, due to their bottom-up approach. One can also clearly see that Algorithm 1 is very fast on strong relations, as expected, but slower than all the others on weak relations. Globally, Algorithm 2c is the fastest, except for relations 14b and 15, where Algorithm 1 is faster. This is the algorithm we recommend using, though one might prefer using Algorithm 1 or 2b in some cases, due to their more concise aspect. The experiment was made on a laptop running Windows 11 on an AMD Ryzen 7 5800U processor at 1.90 GHz.

¹⁰Note that the order of exploration of the tree is important: neighbors have to be explored in the order of the adjacency lists used in our tree data structure (Appendix A.6), otherwise the exploration will not correspond to a DFS search tree. For example, if one explores node 6b before node 4a, one might miss relation 12a as an optimal relation. In other words, the algorithm assumes that, when exploring the branch starting with 6b, the whole branch starting with 4b has already been explored. In contrast, the order of exploration of neighbors played no role in Algorithm 2a, because each node was connected to all the stronger nodes in the DAG, and each node contained the full definition of the relation.

```

def tree_traversal(node, a, b): # a and b are Period objects
    if not condition_short[node](a, b):
        return None
    for neighbor in tree[node]:
        rel = tree_traversal(neighbor, a, b)
        if rel is not None:
            return rel
    return node

def alg2b(a, b): # Algorithm 2b: tree traversal short
    return tree_traversal("0", a, b)

```

(a) Python implementation. The `condition_short` and `tree` structures are detailed in Appendices A.5 and A.6.

(b) Data structure (tree)

FIGURE 4. Algorithm 2b: tree traversal.

5. CASE STUDY

Our case study concerns the Early Bronze Age (EB) in the southern Levant. It is based on a wide radiocarbon study published in 2012, which concluded in a revised chronology for the period (Regev et al. 2012). The study proposes a Bayesian model combining samples from eight sites, covering the EBIA, EBIB, EBII and EBIII periods. It models these periods separately for each site, thus allowing for different dates for the phase transitions at each site. The study’s results (95% confidence ranges for each transition) are illustrated in Table 6. The question that naturally arises is which temporal relations can be deduced from these results. Our approach allows to answer this question in a fast and automated way. The results are shown in Fig. 8, as a matrix providing the strongest relation for every pair of site-period combinations¹¹. We can make the following observations:

¹¹Note that our results stem from a deterministic analysis, which does not take into account the probabilities associated to each range (the ranges are seen as a trustworthy given). For an alternative, probabilistic approach to discovering temporal relations based on radiocarbon results, see Pluckhahn, Wallis, and Thompson 2020, p. 475-476.

```

def alg2c(a, b): # a and b are Period objects
    if a.start <= b.end:
        if a.start <= b.start:
            if a.end <= b.start:
                if a.end == b.start:
                    return "12a"
                return "4a"
            if a.end >= b.start:
                if b.end >= a.end:
                    if b.end == a.end:
                        if a.start == b.start:
                            return "15"
                        return "14b"
                    if a.start == b.start:
                        return "13a"
                    return "8a"
                if a.end >= b.end:
                    if a.start == b.start:
                        return "13b"
                    return "9a"
                if a.start == b.start:
                    return "10"
            return "6b"
        return "2a"
    if a.end <= b.end:
        if a.end >= b.start:
            if a.end == b.end:
                if a.start >= b.start:
                    return "14a"
                return "11"
            if a.start >= b.start:
                return "9b"
            return "7a"
        return "3a"
    if a.end >= b.start:
        if a.end >= b.end:
            if a.start >= b.start:
                if a.start == b.end:
                    return "12b"
                return "8b"
            return "7b"
        if a.start >= b.start:
            return "6a"
        return "5"
    return "1a"
    if a.end >= b.start:
        if a.end >= b.end:
            if a.start >= b.end:
                return "4b"
            return "3b"
        if a.start >= b.start:
            return "2b"
        return "1b"
    return "0"

```

FIGURE 5. Algorithm 4: explicit decision tree.

FIGURE 6. Comparing the four algorithms' execution times, using one million relations selected uniformly at random.

FIGURE 7. Comparison the four algorithms' execution times, relation by relation, using one hundred thousand repetitions of each relation type.

- (1) Over half of the pairs have no relation at all. In some cases, contexts belonging to the same phase (say, EBIB), have no relation at all.
- (2) All the relations are *basic* ones, consisting of a mere ordering between two boundaries (relations 1–4). More complex relations, involving temporal contemporaneity (relations 5–15) are totally absent from the results.
- (3) Some contexts are particularly poor in results: Bahb ed-Drah (IB, II) and Beth Yerah III yielded only three relations, and Kabri II only four.
- (4) One result is noteworthy: the EBII at Beth Yerah (BY II) starts earlier than (rel. 2a) the EBII at Abu al-Kharaz (K) and Yarmuth (Y). This shows that periods are not always synchronized across sites, a conclusion also reached by the authors of the original study.

Site	EBIA/EBIB	EBIB/EBII	EBII/EBIII
Abu al-Kharaz (Kh)	–	3090–2940	–
Ashkelon (A)	3520–3220	–	–
Bahb ed-Drah (D)	–	3220–2520	–
Beth Yerah (BY)	3650–3330	3550–3120	3190–2660
Jericho (J)	–	–	2990–2760
Kabri (K)	3380–3100	3350–3010	–
Yarmuth (Y)	–	3050–2920	3010–2900
Tel el-Umeiri (U)	–	–	3090–2920

TABLE 6. Case study data (based on Regev et al. 2012, p. 549, Table 2). The results represent 95% confidence intervals for the transitions between the EBIA, EBIB, EBII and EBIII periods, respectively. Through lack of space, for every case where more than one variant result was presented by the authors, only one was kept (omitted results are Kharaz (seeds), Ashkelon (seeds), Ashkelon (three-phased version), Jericho (seeds), Yarmouth (seeds)). All dates are BCE.

Results 1-3 are rather negative. One can be surprised that not even one case of contemporaneity between equivalent periods accross different sites could be established. Such negative results could have several explanations: (a) many examined contexts were probably short-lived contexts belonging to long-lived phases, thus augmenting the chance for non-contemporaneity (a conclusion also reached by the authors of the original study), (b) an insufficient number of samples in some contexts (note that each site lacks at least one subperiod), (c) the two plateaus in the calibration curve in our period of interest, yielding large temporal ranges. These few observations were merely given here as an illustration of our method’s potential, combining speed of analysis and exhaustive generation of optimal temporal relations.

Another interesting application of this method is that it allows to view the optimal relations as a directed acyclic graph (DAG), where nodes represent boundaries and edges represent chronological anteriority (i.e., the “earlier or at” relation). Our matrix can be graphically represented by such a DAG, allowing to easily discern patterns among the data. Fig. 9 illustrates the (transitively reduced) DAG of our case study, produced automatically by ChronoLog 3. The DAG allows, for example, to easily identify boundaries sharing no relation with others, such as they are often drawn on the contours of the graph, as beg(Kh IB), end (Kh II), or end(J III) (among others). The DAG also helps identifying central nodes, such as the highly-connected boundaries beg(KH II), beg(A IB), and beg(KIB).

6. CONCLUSION

This paper proposed a practical solution to the problem of finding the optimal temporal relation between two time-periods, in the presence of uncertainties regarding their boundaries (i.e., unknown or bounded start/end). We proposed a fast algorithmic solution, implemented in the Python language. Our solution is simple enough as to be easily translatable into other programming languages, and it is our hope that others will implement it in their own chronological packages. Finally,

Site & EB phase		Kh		A		D		BY			J		K			Y			U	
		IB	II	IA	IB	IB	II	IA	II	III	II	III	IA	IB	II	IB	II	III	II	III
Kh	IB	-	-	3b	1b	-	-	3b	1b	-	-	-	3b	1b	-	-	-	-	-	-
	II	-	-	4b	2b	-	-	4b	2b	-	-	-	4b	2b	-	-	-	-	-	-
A	IA	3a	4a	-	-	3a	4a	-	3a	4a	3a	4a	-	-	-	3a	4a	4a	3a	4a
	IB	1a	2a	-	-	1a	2a	-	1a	2a	1a	2a	-	-	-	1a	2a	2a	1a	2a
D	IB	-	-	3b	1b	-	-	3b	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	II	-	-	4b	2b	-	-	1b	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
BY	IA	3a	4a	-	-	3a	4a	-	3a	4a	3a	4a	-	-	-	3a	4a	4a	3a	4a
	II	1a	2a	3b	1b	-	-	3b	-	-	1a	2a	-	-	-	1a	2a	2a	1a	2a
	III	-	-	4b	2b	-	-	4b	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
J	II	-	-	3b	1b	-	-	3b	1b	-	-	-	3b	3b	1b	-	-	-	-	
	III	-	-	4b	2b	-	-	4b	2b	-	-	-	4b	4b	2b	-	-	-	-	
K	IA	3a	4a	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3a	4a	-	-	-	3a	4a	4a	3a	4a
	IB	1a	2a	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3a	4a	-	-	-	1a	2a	4a	1a	2a
	II	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1a	2a	-	-	-	-	1a	2a	-	-
Y	IB	-	-	3b	1b	-	-	3b	1b	-	-	-	3b	1b	-	-	-	-	-	
	II	-	-	4b	2b	-	-	4b	2b	-	-	-	4b	3b	1b	-	-	-	-	
	III	-	-	4b	2b	-	-	4b	2b	-	-	-	4b	4b	2b	-	-	-	-	
U	II	-	-	3b	1b	-	-	3b	1b	-	-	-	3b	1b	-	-	-	-	-	
	III	-	-	4b	2b	-	-	4b	2b	-	-	-	4b	2b	-	-	-	-	-	

FIGURE 8. Case study results. Cell contents refer to our temporal relations IDs (Table 1). Site name are abbreviated are according to Table 6.

we also proposed a short case study, related to radiocarbon results on the Early Bronze Age in the Levant, to illustrate the practical applicability of our method.

This paper entered into quite a few technical details describing the optimization of our algorithms. One could wonder why bother optimizing execution speed on an algorithm that explores a constant-size graph. It is true that such minute optimizations would be unnecessary if one were to execute the algorithm only once. Yet, chronological software may need to deal with thousands of time-periods, thus potentially millions of pairwise temporal relations. Under such large datasets, high execution speed is of paramount importance. The latest version of ChronoLog (v. 3, released 8 June, 2026), includes such an automated fast computation of the strongest temporal relations between all pairs of periods in a model, using Algorithm 2c described above.

FIGURE 9. Case study: directed acyclic graph (DAG) showing the anteriority relations (“earlier or at”) between all the boundaries. The DAG has been transitively reduced (image generated by ChronoLog 3).

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APPENDIX A. PYTHON CODE

A.1. The Boundary class

```
class Boundary:
    def __init__(self, lb=None, ub=None):
        if lb is not None and ub is not None and lb > ub:
            raise ValueError("Lower bound cannot exceed upper bound")
        self.lb = lb # lower bound
        self.ub = ub # upper bound

    def __eq__(self, other): # equals operator
        return (self.lb is not None and self.ub is not None
                and self.lb == other.lb and self.ub == other.ub)

    def __le__(self, other): # lower or equal operator
        return (self.ub is not None and other.lb is not None
                and self.ub <= other.lb)

    def __ge__(self, other): # greater or equal operator
        return (self.lb is not None and other.ub is not None
                and self.lb >= other.ub)

    def __str__(self): # conversion to string
        if self.lb == self.ub: # known value
            return str(self.lb)
        else:
            return "[" + str(self.lb) + "," + str(self.ub) + "]"

    def __repr__(self): # for printing
        return self.__str__()

class After(Boundary): # Terminus Post Quem
    def __init__(self, lb):
        self.lb = lb
        self.ub = None

class Before(Boundary): # Terminus Ante Quem
    def __init__(self, ub):
        self.lb = None
        self.ub = ub

class Range(Boundary): # Range
    def __init__(self, lb, ub):
        self.lb = lb
        self.ub = ub
```

A.2. The Period class

```
class Period:
    def __init__(self, start=None, end=None):
        # Initialize start
        if start is None:
            self.start = Boundary()
        elif isinstance(start, int):
            self.start = Boundary(start, start)
        elif isinstance(start, Boundary):
            self.start = start
        else:
            raise ValueError("Wrong start: use None, int or Boundary")

        # Initialize end
        if end is None:
            self.end = Boundary()
        elif isinstance(end, int):
            self.end = Boundary(end, end)
        elif isinstance(end, Boundary):
            self.end = end
        else:
            raise ValueError("Wrong end: use None, int or Boundary")

        # Ensure that the end's lower bound equals at least the
        # start's lower bound
        if self.start.lb is not None and \
            (self.end.lb is None or self.end.lb < self.start.lb):
            self.end.lb = self.start.lb

        # Ensure that the start's upper bound equals at most the
        # end's upper bound
        if self.end.ub is not None and \
            (self.start.ub is None or self.start.ub > self.end.ub):
            self.start.ub = self.end.ub

    def __str__(self): # conversion to string
        return "{start=" + str(self.start) \
            + ", end=" + str(self.end) + "}"

    def __repr__(self): # for printing
        return self.__str__()
```

A.3. Full conditions (algorithms 1 and 2a)

Python implementation of the full conditions defining our 15 relations:

```
condition = {}
condition["0"] = lambda a,b: True
condition["1a"] = lambda a,b: a.start <= b.end
condition["1b"] = lambda a,b: a.end >= b.start
condition["2a"] = lambda a,b: a.start <= b.start
condition["2b"] = lambda a,b: a.start >= b.start
condition["3a"] = lambda a,b: a.end <= b.end
condition["3b"] = lambda a,b: a.end >= b.end
condition["4a"] = lambda a,b: a.end <= b.start
condition["4b"] = lambda a,b: a.start >= b.end
condition["5"] = lambda a,b: a.start <= b.end and a.end >= b.start
condition["6a"] = lambda a,b: a.start >= b.start and a.start <= b.end
condition["6b"] = lambda a,b: a.start <= b.start and a.end >= b.start
condition["7a"] = lambda a,b: a.end >= b.start and a.end <= b.end
condition["7b"] = lambda a,b: a.start <= b.end and a.end >= b.end
condition["8a"] = lambda a,b: a.start <= b.start \
    and a.end >= b.start \
    and a.end <= b.end
condition["8b"] = lambda a,b: b.start <= a.start \
    and b.end >= a.start \
    and b.end <= a.end
condition["9a"] = lambda a,b: a.start <= b.start and a.end >= b.end
condition["9b"] = lambda a,b: b.start <= a.start and b.end >= a.end
condition["10"] = lambda a,b: a.start == b.start
condition["11"] = lambda a,b: a.end == b.end
condition["12a"] = lambda a,b: a.end == b.start
condition["12b"] = lambda a,b: a.start == b.end
condition["13a"] = lambda a,b: a.start == b.start and a.end <= b.end
condition["13b"] = lambda a,b: a.start == b.start and a.end >= b.end
condition["14a"] = lambda a,b: a.end == b.end and a.start >= b.start
condition["14b"] = lambda a,b: a.end == b.end and a.start <= b.start
condition["15"] = lambda a,b: a.start == b.start and a.end == b.end
```

A.4. Python implementation of the inverted DAG (algorithm 2a)

```
graph = {}
graph["0"] = ["1a", "1b"] # "no relation"
graph["1a"] = ["2a", "3a", "5"] # "starts before or at end of"
graph["1b"] = ["5", "3b", "2b"] # "ends after or at start of"
graph["2a"] = ["4a", "6b"] # "starts bef. or at start of"
graph["2b"] = ["6a", "4b"] # "starts aft. or at start of"
graph["3a"] = ["4a", "7a"] # "ends before or at end of"
graph["3b"] = ["7b", "4b"] # "ends after or at end of"
graph["4a"] = ["12a"] # "ends before or at start of"
graph["4b"] = ["12b"] # "starts after or at end of"
graph["5"] = ["6b", "7a", "7b", "6a"] # "contemporary"
graph["6a"] = ["10", "9b", "8b"] # "starts during"
graph["6b"] = ["8a", "9a", "10"] # "includes start of"
graph["7a"] = ["8a", "11", "9b"] # "ends during"
graph["7b"] = ["9a", "11", "8b"] # "includes end of"
graph["8a"] = ["12a", "14b", "13a"] # "overlaps before"
graph["8b"] = ["13b", "14a", "12b"] # "overlaps after"
graph["9a"] = ["14b", "13b"] # "includes"
graph["9b"] = ["13a", "14a"] # "included in"
graph["10"] = ["13a", "13b"] # "equal start"
graph["11"] = ["14b", "14a"] # "equal end"
graph["12a"] = [] # "meets"
graph["12b"] = [] # "met by"
graph["13a"] = ["15"] # "begins"
graph["13b"] = ["15"] # "begun by"
graph["14a"] = ["15"] # "ends"
graph["14b"] = ["15"] # "ended by"
graph["15"] = [] # "equal"
```

A.5. Shortened conditions (algorithm 2c)

```
condition_short["0"] = lambda a,b: True
condition_short["1a"] = lambda a,b: a.start <= b.end
condition_short["1b"] = lambda a,b: a.end >= b.start
condition_short["2a"] = lambda a,b: a.start <= b.start
condition_short["2b"] = lambda a,b: a.start >= b.start
condition_short["3a"] = lambda a,b: a.end <= b.end
condition_short["3b"] = lambda a,b: a.end >= b.end
condition_short["4a"] = lambda a,b: a.end <= b.start
condition_short["4b"] = lambda a,b: a.start >= b.end
condition_short["5"] = lambda a,b: a.end >= b.start
condition_short["6a"] = lambda a,b: a.start >= b.start
condition_short["6b"] = lambda a,b: a.end >= b.start
condition_short["7a"] = lambda a,b: a.end >= b.start
condition_short["7b"] = lambda a,b: a.end >= b.end
condition_short["8a"] = lambda a,b: a.end <= b.end
condition_short["8b"] = lambda a,b: b.start <= a.start
condition_short["9a"] = lambda a,b: a.end >= b.end
condition_short["9b"] = lambda a,b: b.start <= a.start
condition_short["10"] = lambda a,b: a.start == b.start
condition_short["11"] = lambda a,b: a.end == b.end
condition_short["12a"] = lambda a,b: a.end == b.start
condition_short["12b"] = lambda a,b: a.start == b.end
condition_short["13a"] = lambda a,b: a.start == b.start
condition_short["13b"] = lambda a,b: a.start == b.start
condition_short["14a"] = lambda a,b: a.start >= b.start
condition_short["14b"] = lambda a,b: a.end == b.end
condition_short["15"] = lambda a,b: a.start == b.start
```

A.6. Python implementation of the DFS tree (algorithm 2c)

```
tree = {}
tree["0"] = ["1a", "1b"] # "no relation"
tree["1a"] = ["2a", "3a", "5"] # "starts before or at end of"
tree["1b"] = ["3b", "2b"] # "ends after or at start of"
tree["2a"] = ["4a", "6b"] # "starts before or at start of"
tree["2b"] = [] # "starts after or at start of"
tree["3a"] = ["7a"] # "ends before or at end of"
tree["3b"] = ["4b"] # "ends after or at end of"
tree["4a"] = ["12a"] # "ends before or at start of"
tree["4b"] = [] # "starts after or at end of"
tree["5"] = ["7b", "6a"] # "contemporary"
tree["6a"] = [] # "starts during"
tree["6b"] = ["8a", "9a", "10"] # "includes start of"
tree["7a"] = ["11", "9b"] # "ends during"
tree["7b"] = ["8b"] # "includes end of"
tree["8a"] = ["14b", "13a"] # "overlaps before"
tree["8b"] = ["12b"] # "overlaps after"
tree["9a"] = ["13b"] # "includes"
tree["9b"] = [] # "included in"
tree["10"] = [] # "equal start"
tree["11"] = ["14a"] # "equal end"
tree["12a"] = [] # "meets"
tree["12b"] = [] # "met by"
tree["13a"] = [] # "begins"
tree["13b"] = [] # "begun by"
tree["14a"] = [] # "ends"
tree["14b"] = ["15"] # "ended by"
tree["15"] = [] # "equal"
```